

ISic3033

I.Sicily inscription 3033

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mazara

Place of origin (modern)

Mazara del Vallo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mazara del Vallo, Cathedral

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108006

1. Τύμβ(ος) ἐν Θ(ε)ῶ κειμένων ἐνθάδε ἐν ἀναπαύ
2. σει· Κωνσταντίνου ζήσαντος ἔτη ιβ', Μελλώ
3. σου ζήσαντος ἔτη ι', κ(αὶ) Νικήτα ζήσαντος ἔτη η'.
4. Τούτων μνήσθητι, Κ(ύρι)ε, ἐν τῇ βασιλείᾳ σου.
5. Ἐτελειώθησαν μη(νὶ) Δεκεμβρίῳ κζ',
6. Ἰνδ(ικτιῶνος) ἕκτης

Edition: PHI332350

1. □ τύμβ(ος) #⁵⁶ ἐν θ(ε)ῶ κειμένων ἐνθάδε ἐν ἀναπαύ-
2. σει #⁵⁶ Κωνσταντίνου ζήσαντος ἔτη ιβ' #⁵⁶ Μελλώ-
3. σου ζήσαντος ἔτη ι' #⁵⁶ κ(αὶ) Νικήτα ζήσαντος ἔτη #⁵⁶ η'.
4. τούτων μνήσθητι, Κ(ύρι)ε, ἐν τῇ βασιλείᾳ σου.
5. ἐτελειώθησαν μη(νὶ) Δεκεμβρίῳ #⁵⁶ κζ' #⁵⁶
6. Ἰνδ(ικτιῶνος) #⁵⁶ ἕκτης. ²palma²
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284812

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EDCS 64600116

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Bibliography

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